

Research

Effect of Welding Speed on Formation and Tensile Strength of 6005A Aluminum Alloy FSW Joint

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Abstract: *In this paper, carrying out the friction stir welding experiment of 6005A aluminum alloy, to explore the influence of welding speed on welding quality. By Studying and observing the macrostructure, it was found that the higher welding speed extracted with lower burs and flash effect. Observing, microscopic view, the grain (molecular structures) formed a closer bond which was representing stronger and mature bonding. The melting stage generates higher spontaneous movement and more frequent inter-bonding. Which was representing the speed unit (500 mm/min) was more efficient and relevant to work on. Micro hardness was analyzed considerably as well. The crystal grain was smaller in stir zone (welding nugget) due to the heat but elongation tensile strength was quite higher in terms of higher welding speed. In the meantime, the middle stage of the micro hardness test graph showed quite higher hardens considering other parameters of welding speed.*

Keywords: *FSW; Manufacturing Waste Reduction; Welding Speed; Industrial Engineering; Tensile Strength.*

Introduction

Because of excellent characteristics of Aluminum Alloys such as high strength to weight ratio, low density, superior resistance to corrosion, excellent extrusion plasticity, adequate formability, finishing characteristics for anodizing or paint and moderate to high fracture toughness. For several reason, FSW is suitable for the welding of 6005A aluminum alloy.

Friction stir welding, as a green solid-phase joining technology, can effectively solve the problems of pores and thermal cracks in traditional fusion welding, severe joint strength loss, and large deformation of thin-walled structures. Technical difficulties, promote the lightweight and

high-quality development of various types of new equipment such as aerospace vehicles, ships, vehicles, etc., and have an outstanding effect on energy saving, emission reduction, quality improvement and efficiency improvement of related industries, which is in line with the aviation, aerospace and other manufacturing development strategies Claim.

The objective of this study is to obtain the optimal welding speed and maximum tensile strength in 6005A-T6 aluminum alloy welded joints regarding Formation, Mechanical structure and Microscopic structure as well at different rotational speed to get the better output for better manufacturing.

Experiment

In this chapter, we will discuss about experimental materials, procedures and techniques. In the preliminary section, we will join the alloy sheets and then we will make macro structure, microstructure and mechanical analysis for convenient experiment in different aspects.

The base metal used in this work was 6005A-T6 Aluminum Alloy for investigating its properties such as tensile strength, yield strength, percentage elongation, hardness, macrostructure and microstructure. In this work, the aluminum 6005A-T6 alloy test plates having the dimension of 300 mm × 100 mm × 3.2-4 mm, prepared by machining, cutting and milling processes is considered for investigation.

Table 1 Chemical Composition of 6005A-T6 Al Alloy

Material	Composition wt %								
6005A	Mg	Si	Mn	Ti	Cr	Zn	Fe	Cu	Al
	0.4-0.6	0.6-0.9	0.1	0.01	≤0.01	≤ 0.10	≤ 0.35	≤0.01	Bal.

Table 2 Mechanical Properties of 6005A-T6 Al Alloy

Material	Yield strength / MPa	Tensile Strength / MPa	Elongation / %
6005A-T6	208.84	275.11	11.63

In FSW, the tool material is plays an important role in determining the quality of the welded joints being produced. The selection of the tool material is dependent on the material of the parent metal to be welded for the different combinations of rotational speeds and feed rates. A non-consumable tool (W9Mo3Cr4V) made of steel is taken as the tool material for the present work. It is heat treatable and will offer hardness, and is machine-able in the annealed condition.

Table 3 Chemical composition of W9Mo3Cr4V steel

Mass fraction / %									
C	W	Mo	Cr	V	Si	Mn	S	P	Fe
0.77-0.87	8.50-9.50	2.70-3.30	3.80-4.40	1.30-1.70	0.20-0.40	0.20-0.40	≤0.30	≤0.30	Bal.

Table 4 Heat treatment details of the tool

Quenchant	Preheating	Salt bath furnace	Oil cooling	Tempering (2h Each time)
820~870°C	120~1230°C	1220~1240°C	540~560°C	Twice

After a relevant study, the tool pin geometries selected conical shape. The photographic view of tool is shown in Fig1 and the tool pin specifications and dimensions are listed in table 5.

Fig1 Tool pin

Table 5 Tool pin specifications and dimensions

Six concave inner helix / mm			Tapper stirring pin /mm			
Shoulder diameter	Slot width	Pitch	Bottom Diameter	Tip diameter	Pitch	Slot width
10	0.8	1.5	5	3	0.8	0.5

The specimen is welded based on the previous literatures and it is shown in the Table 6.

Table 6 Process parameters and its values

Process parameters	Values
Tool rotation speed	1500 rpm
Welding speed	200, 300, 400, 500, 600 mm/min
Tool displacement	30 cm
Dwell time	1.5 s
Tool tilt	2.5°
Plunge depth	0.2 mm

For various forms of welding, the main technical specifications are shown in Table 7. In order to achieve the rigid fixation of the workpiece to be welded in the friction stir welding process, the

tooling fixture is used to clamp the workpiece to ensure that the welding proceeds smoothly. The material of the base and the pressing bolt is Q235, and the material of the pressing steel bar is 45 steel.

Table 7 Main Technical Specifications of FSW Machine

Name	Values
X Maximum stroke	1500 mm
Y Maximum stroke	800 mm
Z Maximum stroke	300 mm
Maximum spindle speed	2000 rpm

After the welding, the metallographic samples were cut perpendicular to the welding direction using electrical discharge wire cutting machine for avoiding thermal degradation. The samples were mechanically mounted and polished. After corrosion for 30s. The metallographic structure was observed under a metallographic microscope. Tensile test pieces were prepared with the tensile direction perpendicular to the welding direction according to GB/T 2653-2008 (ISO5173:2000, IDT), so that the weld zone is located in the middle of the specimen. The room temperature tensile rate is 5 mm/min. Uses 180 #, 400 #, 800 # and 1200 # sandpaper in order to polish the surface of the test piece; to eliminate the scratches on the surface of the test piece, prevent stress concentration due to defects during the test, and affect the test accuracy. Vickers hardness of the joints was measured at the mid-thickness perpendicular to the welding direction.

Result and Discussion

Surface Forming

Flash defect is an unavoidable surface defect in friction stir welding process. Therefore, when the sample is tested for performance, the surface should be treated to remove flash. Factors such as weld misalignment are also important reasons for flash during butt joint. Although the generation of flash does not have certain regularity in the welding process, it has certain regularity from the final appearance. The flash is always generated on the front side of the shaft shoulder of the stirring head and formed on one or both sides of the weld. According to the different morphology of the flash formed at the weld, it can be divided into two categories: fracture flash and adhesion flash. The fracture flash appearance and the adhesion flash appearance are shown in Fig2 and Fig3 respectively.

(a) Clastic fracture (b) Spiral fracture (c) Banded fracture

Fig2 Fracture flash morphology

(a) Filamentous adhesion (b) Broken adhesion (c) Complete adhesion

Fig3 Adhesive flash profile

The influence of different welding speeds on flash and arc is analyzed:

Firstly, according to these five groups of different welding speed parameters, three groups of typical parameters are selected from the surface morphology obtained after welding for preliminary analysis. According to these five groups of parameters, the surface morphology in the steady state stage is selected to analyze the size, type and characteristics of flash and arc formation. The mechanism of flash and arc defects in friction stir welding joints is discussed. The topography of the five parameters are shown in Fig4.

(a) 200 mm/min

(b) 300 mm/min

(c) 400 mm/min

(d) 500 mm/min

(e) 600 mm/min

Fig4 Surface morphology at steady stage

According to the surface morphology in fig4, the mechanism of flash generation and arc formation is very complicated. When other conditions remain unchanged, the welding speed directly affects the heat input and the stirring degree of plasticized metal in the welding process, thus affecting the surface morphology of the welded joint.

It can be seen from the figure that the surface topography corresponding to the five groups of parameters is very different in the steady state stage, and the flash edge and arc grain have their own characteristics. The flash edge formed in Fig (a) is the largest and continuous, and no fracture occurs. It belongs to the flash edge type of complete adhesion, and the flash edge is concentrated on the retreating side. The distance between the arc patterns formed on the surface is relatively wide, and the arc patterns in the welding nugget area show uniform fish scale patterns. The flash edge generated in Fig (b) is smaller than Fig (a) and presents clastic shape, which belongs to clastic fracture in the broken flash edge. The flash edge is concentrated on the upper side of the weld line. The arc lines formed on the surface are fuzzy and the surface lines are rough. Fish scale lines are basically invisible, and burrs can be obviously found on the surface. The flash produced in Fig (c) is relatively small with obvious fracture marks. The type of flash belongs to fracture adhesion and is concentrated on the retreating side. The arc lines formed on the surface show uniform fish scale lines and the distance between the arc lines is smaller than Fig (a), and there is no surface burr as shown in Fig (b). Fig (d) has no flash, the surface is relatively smooth, and the fish scale lines are closely and evenly arranged. The flash produced in Fig (e) is small and is filamentous adhesion, mainly concentrated on the upper side of the weld, with no burrs on the surface, uniform distribution of fish scale lines and larger spacing than Fig (d).

Microstructure Characteristics

Fig5 the base metal is an extruded profile. During the forming process, the grains and intergranular substances are elongated along the rolling direction to form a long or lath-shaped rolling structure with coarse grains. The figure is a macroscopic photograph of the cross section of the welded joint. From Fig6, five different areas can be observed, namely, the Weld Nugget/ Stir Zone (NZ), the Thermo-Mechanically Affected Zone (TMAZ), the Heat or Thermally Affected Zone (HAZ) and the shoulder affected Zone (SAZ). The middle part of the weld is the weld nugget zone, whose shape and size are similar to those of the stirring head. This zone is subjected to the combined action of friction heat and machinery, and the temperature rises and strong plastic deformation occurs.

Fig5 Structure of base metal

Fig6 Cross-sectional morphology of welded joints (a=Weld Nugget, b=Heat Affected Zone, c=Unaffected Material, d=Thermo-mechanically affected zone, RS=Retreating Side, AS=Advancing Side).

Weld Nugget Zone

The welding nugget zone is located in the central area of the weld and is mainly affected by the stirring pin. During the welding process, the weld nugget material undergoes severe plastic deformation and high temperature. As can be seen from Fig7, the microstructure of the weld nugget region is completely different from the rolled microstructure of the base metal and has evolved into equiaxed microstructure with uniform grain size. FSW is a thermal deformation process. When the rotating speed is high or the welding speed is slow, the friction heat obtained in the welding nugget zone is high. Under the intense stirring and friction heat action of the material by the stirring tool, the temperature of the welding nugget exceeds the dissolution temperature of the precipitation strengthening phase, but is lower than its melting temperature. Under high temperature, large deformation and high deformation speed, dislocation density in grains increases sharply, and many cellular substructures are formed, which become the core of recrystallization, form recrystallized grains, and finally obtain fine equiaxed grains. In addition, during the welding process, the stirring head also has a certain crushing effect on the grains, so the structure in the welding nugget region is a recrystallization structure of large deformation metal. Due to the high thermal conductivity of aluminum alloy, the temperature drops rapidly and there is also a temperature gradient, which makes recrystallization incomplete and weld nugget structure uneven.

Fig7 Microstructure of welding nugget

Comparing the weld nugget structure under different welding process parameters shown in Fig8, it is found that under the condition of a certain rotation speed of the stirring head, the grain size increases with the increase of welding speed. However, on the other hand, with the decrease of welding heat input, the grain growth time is reduced, which will also inhibit the grain growth. Therefore, the comprehensive effect of the two aspects results in insignificant grain size change.

Fig8 Microstructure of welding nugget under different process parameters

Thermo-Mechanically Affected Zone

Fig9 are topographical diagrams of the thermo-mechanically affected zone under typical processes. Notification can be analyzed that the material migration amount in the thermo-mechanically affected area on the forward side of the weld is larger than the backward side. The amount of material migration in the thermo-mechanically affected zone near the surface of the weldment is very large, and the amount of material migration in the thermo-mechanically affected zone near the back of the weldment is close to 0. In the welding process, the flash size of the backward side is larger than the forward side, thus causing more heat loss and causing the temperature of the forward side to be higher than the backward side. Therefore, the material in the thermo-mechanically affected zone of the forward side is more prone to deformation and more displacement under the action of material flow in the welding nugget zone. The material near the weldment surface mainly flows under the action of the shaft shoulder. On the one hand, the larger linear velocity of each point of the shaft shoulder is conducive to increasing the material flow in the nearby area; the downward pressure of the shaft shoulder will also cause the material to migrate downward. The combination of the two makes the material migration near the thermo-mechanically affected area of the weldment surface very large.

(a) Retreating side proximal surface

(b) Advancing side proximal surface

(c) Backward side near bottom surface

(d) Forward side near bottom surface

Fig9 Topography of FSW thermo-mechanically affected zone

At the same time, for the materials near the back of the weldment, the materials in the weld nugget zone move downward under the drive of the spiral stirring pin and accumulate near the back of the weldment. With the increase of the stacking amount, the stacking materials migrate to the thermo-mechanically affected zone on the forward side or the backward side, causing the materials in the thermo-mechanically affected zone to migrate upward. At the same time, the downward movement of the material in the welding nugget zone will also affect the material in the heat affected zone, making it tend to move downward. The combined effect of the two makes the material migration amount on the forward side or backward side near the back of the weldment very small or even at 0.

Tensile Properties

During the tensile process of the sample, the material enters the strengthening stage after passing through the yield stage. As the transverse cross-sectional size is obviously reduced, the maximum force borne during tensile fracture is divided by the stress obtained by the original cross-sectional area of the sample, which is called tensile strength or strength limit, and the unit is N/mm^2 (MPa). It represents the maximum ability of metal materials to resist damage under tensile force. The calculation formula is:

$$\sigma = F_b/S \quad (3.1)$$

Where, σ =Tensile strength; F_b =The maximum force that the specimen bears when it is tensioned and broken: -N; S =Original cross-sectional area of the sample, mm^2 .

When the material yields to a certain degree, its deformation resistance is improved again due to the rearrangement of internal grains. Although deformation develops rapidly at this time, it can only increase with the increase of stress until the stress reaches the maximum value. After that, the ability of the material to resist deformation is obviously reduced, and a large plastic deformation occurs at the weakest part, where the section of the specimen shrinks rapidly and necks until fracture. The maximum stress value before tensile fracture of a material is called strength limit or tensile strength.

During the bending sample test, the bending angle is not less than 150° , and the pressure judgment standard is that the crack is not more than 3 mm, which is qualified. In order to compare the strength values between the welded joint and the base metal, the strength test of the base metal was carried out at first. As shown in Fig10, a test plate was randomly selected and three tensile samples were taken by wire cutting for testing. The tensile strength of the base metal was 298 MPa and the elongation was 9.7%.

Fig10 Tensile testing sample

Tensile properties of welded test plates were tested according to relevant standards, and the test results are shown in Table 9. In the welded state, the microstructure strength in the weld nugget zone of friction stir welding joint is higher than the heat affected zone. For aluminum alloy strengthened by heat treatment, the microstructure strength at the junction between the heat affected zone, the thermo-mechanically affected zone and the weld nugget zone after friction stir welding is lower, so joint fracture often occurs here.

Table 8 Mechanical Properties of 6005A-T6 Aluminum Alloy

E.N	Tensile strength R_m (MPa)	Elongation A (%)
1	290	9.2
2	302	9.8
3	302	10.0
Average	298	9.7

Table 9 Mechanical properties of welded joints

E.N	Rotational speed ω / (rpm)	welding speed v /(mm/min)	Tensile strength R_m (MPa)	Elongation A (%)	Fracture location	Strength coefficient
Base Metal	—	—	298	9.7	—	—
S4-1	1500	200	201	5.3	Weld line	0.67
			178	5.2	Weld line	0.59
	Average		190	5.3		0.63
S4-2	1500	300	215	6.1	Weld line	0.72
			219	6.4	Weld line	0.73
	Average		217	6.3		0.73
S4-3	1500	400	222	7.3	Weld line	0.75
			231	6.6	Weld line	0.78
	Average		227	7.0		0.76
S4-5	1500	500	224	7.1	Weld line	0.75
			216	7.2	Weld line	0.72
	Average		220	7.2		0.74
S4-6	1500	600	215	6.3	Weld line	0.72
			201	6.7	Weld line	0.67
	Average		208	6.5		0.70

According to Table 9, the tensile strength and strength coefficient of the joint at five welding speeds are selected for comparative analysis. It is found that with the increase of welding speed, the strength increases first and then decreases.

Micro hardness

The microstructure changes after friction stir processing are complex, it is influenced by many factors such as machining tools, machining technology and properties of each materials, previous studies have shown that the microstructure after friction stir processing is between the advancing side and the backward side of the stirring zone. Most of these zones have fuzzy interfaces and narrow zones, which is not conducive to performance research. Therefore, hardness test has become an effective means to understand the changes of microstructure and properties. Mainly, it reflects two aspects of information. Firstly, the change of hardness distribution directly reflects the change rule of mechanical properties caused by the microstructure of the processing area. Secondly, it can indirectly reflect the influence law of material rheological field and temperature field changes on the microstructure, especially the morphology distribution of the second phase. The micro hardness of the material is mainly affected by the size of the material grain, the number and size of dislocation density, the number distribution and size of precipitated phase, the changes

of rheological field and temperature field of the material, etc. The average hardness of the base metal is 95.4 HV.

Hardness analysis

Fig11 shows the hardness change curve of weld cross section at different welding speeds when the rotating speed is 1500 rpm. It can be seen from the comparison of Fig11 (a), (b) and (c) that the hardness distribution of the weld and its surrounding materials is approximately the same under each parameter. The hardness distribution of the welded line area at the welding speed of 300 mm/min presents a "W" shape, and the hardness changes from the center of the weld to both sides of the weld approximately show a law of decreasing first and then increasing. The hardness of the base metal (about 100 HV) is the highest, the hardness of the weld nugget area is higher than the thermo-mechanically affected zone and the heat affected zone, and the minimum hardness value appears in the heat affected zone.

The hardness curve shows "W" or "U" shape because 6005A belongs to aging strengthened aluminum alloy. The mechanical properties are not only related to the distribution and size of reinforced phase, but also affected by grain size. The aging process of Al-Mg-Si alloy is as follows: supersaturated solid solution-GP region— β'' — β' — β , β'' the phase and the matrix maintain a coherent relationship, and its reinforcement effect is the best. When the β' phase or β phase occurs, it is called over-aging state, and the enhancement effect begins to deteriorate. The 6005A-T6 base metal contains a large number of pin-like β'' phases, which is in the state of peak aging and has the greatest reinforcement effect, with a hardness of about 95 HV. The β'' phase in the heat affected zone dissolves in the matrix and precipitates coarse β'' phase, thus significantly reducing its hardness. The thermo-mechanically affected zone is also in an over-aged state, but its grain specific heat affected zone is small, and the zone has undergone plastic deformation and contains dislocations with higher density, so the hardness value is slightly higher than the heat affected zone. Almost all the particles in the weld nugget zone are solid dissolved in the matrix, and the hardness in the weld nugget zone is close to natural aging during the welding process, so the hardness in the weld nugget zone is improved. At the same time, the fine equiaxed crystals in the weld nugget zone also compensate for some hardness loss, so the hardness in the weld nugget zone is higher than the heat affected zone and the thermo-mechanically affected zone, thus making the hardness curve show a "W" shape.

When the welding speed is 300 mm/min (Fig11 a), the average hardness (69 HV) of the material at the detection line on the weld is about 72.3% of the hardness of the base metal, which is higher than the average hardness of the material at the detection line and the lower detection line in the weld nugget. The highest hardness point of the weld occurs at the upper detection line on the return side of the thermo-mechanically affected zone. The average hardness (64.5 HV) at the detection line under the weld is the lowest, which is about 67.6% of the base metal. The lowest hardness occurs on the middle detection line near the heat affected zone of the weld. Under this parameter, the hardness of the forward side and the backward side are not much different. There is not much difference in the hardness of the materials at the upper detection line, the middle detection line and the lower detection line in the weld area with welding speeds of 400 mm/min (Fig11 b) and 500 mm/min (Fig11 c), indicating that the hardness of the materials in the weld area is evenly distributed longitudinally. The hardness of the upper, middle and lower three test lines of the three groups of parameters is observed. The hardness value of the upper region is generally slightly higher than the lower part of the weld. Analysis shows that the grain refinement degree of the material on the upper surface of the weld is higher under the combined action of the shaft shoulder and the stirring pin. According to Hall-Petch formula:

$$HV_{150} = 189.03 \times 10^3 \times F/d^2 \quad (3.2)$$

Where,

F=Loading force

D=Diagonal length of indentation.

Therefore, the refinement of crystal grains improves the hardness of the material.

Fig11 Hardness curves

Conclusions

The formation, microstructure and mechanical properties of 6005A-T6 Friction Stir Welded 300 mm × 100 mm × 3.2-4 mm aluminum alloy sheets using different welding parameters have been studied. From this investigation, the following conclusions can be extracted:

(1) The 6005A aluminum alloy is more alloyed comparing other aluminum alloys, this characteristic is certainly provided more accurate output. (2) Controlling the vibration during the FWS process the flash problem can be solved partially. (3) Considering all the marco structure mentioned speed unit (500 mm/min) appeared with the least flash and the smallest burs. The unit will be studied further to execute better results. (4) The grains (molecular particles of the workpiece) made a stronger bond by melting with the high temperature generated with the speed. The melting stage generates higher spontaneous movement and more frequent inter-bonding. Which was representing the speed unit (500 mm/min) was more efficient and relevant to work on. (5) Observing the rotating speed (1500 rpm) and welding speed (500 mm/min) the more convenient tensile strength (224 MPa) was allocated; Higher elongation (7.1%) was found; Strength coefficient (0.75) was found which indicates these working parameters are showing more possibility to get better output. (6) Aerospace technology can be formatted according to the usability and of friction stir welding in a comprehensive way comparing inclusive and effective formability and elongation, which will improve the plasticity and heat treatment function observing the hardness curve (500 mm/min). The dropping possibility is comparably low. (7) Waste reduction may possible either by considering rotating speed (1500 rpm) and welding speed (500 mm/min) the more convenient tensile strength (224 MPa) which provide us better output or even it produce fewer burs and flash.

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Conflicts of Interest

All authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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